

Research Article

Innovative Teaching Approach: Product Adaptation in International Agricultural Marketing

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Abstract: *This paper presents an innovative teaching approach that uses the official websites of McDonald's and KFC from different countries to demonstrate product adaptation in international agricultural marketing. Despite the significance of product adaptation in international marketing, many students struggle to grasp how global brands effectively tailor their offerings to meet diverse cultural and consumer needs. Traditional teaching methods often fail to provide students with practical, real-world examples that illustrate these concepts, hindering their understanding of the dynamic nature of international markets and the strategies employed by multinational companies. To address this gap, students are guided to explore how these global brands modify their product offerings based on cultural, regulatory, and consumer demands. By analyzing online menus from various regions, students can gain firsthand insight into the implementation of product adaptation. Multimedia tools and collaborative platforms enhance the learning experience by encouraging critical thinking and practical application.*

Keywords: *Teaching Innovation; Product Adaptation; International Agriculture Marketing.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

In traditional international agricultural marketing courses, students often struggle to grasp the practical applications of product adaptation across global markets. Textbooks and lectures typically provide theoretical frameworks, but they fail to immerse students in real-world scenarios where cultural, regulatory, and consumer preferences dictate how global brands modify their offerings (Ritzer, 2010). Marketing education is having issues with the involvement of students in traditional

learning activities, e.g., lecture classes with textbooks, slides and video (Casado-Aranda et al., 2021). Students' engagement and motivation are hindered by lecture-focused classes, outdated content, difficulty applying digital technologies, and a silo approach, which limits integrated learning and active teaching methodologies in the digital curriculum (Casado-Aranda et al., 2021). This gap between theory and practice hinders students' ability to critically analyze and apply international marketing strategies in a dynamic, global context (Griffith & Rubera, 2014). Moreover, active learning and engagement can also be achieved in marketing curricula with design game elements and mechanics, to prepare students for the situation analysis stage of the marketing planning process (Harding & Alexander, 2019). Therefore, demanded by the complex and dynamic marketplace, there exist a current need to assess diverse ways of knowledge creation, to integrate the gap between theory and practice (Molin & Sjöberg, 2017).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Website Exploration for Product Adaptation

McDonalds and KFC Websites: Students are tasked with visiting the official websites of McDonald's and KFC in different countries (e.g., USA, Japan, India, and UAE). This exploration reveals how menus differ significantly in terms of local specialties, ingredient choices, and product names. For instance, McDonald's offers the "McArabia" in the Middle East, the "Teriyaki Burger" in Japan, and the "McSpicy Paneer" in India. KFC also offers unique regional items, such as "Zinger Rice Box" in Malaysia or "Hot Wings" with local flavors in South Africa.

- McDonald's Japan: <https://www.mcdonalds.co.jp>
- McDonald's India: <https://www.mcdonaldsindia.com>
- McDonald's UAE: <https://www.mcdelivery.ae/>
- KFC China: <https://www.kfc.com.cn>
- KFC India: https://www.instagram.com/kfcindia_official/?hl=en
- KFC Indonesia: <https://kfcku.com/>

Students will compare the menus and analyze why these products are available in some countries but not in others, considering factors like local preferences, dietary restrictions, and regional market regulations.

2.2 Collaborative Learning Tools

Google Classroom: Students submit their findings on product adaptations from the websites and participate in group discussions on Google Classroom, sharing their insights and comparing their findings across different countries.

3. FINDINGS

The thematic analysis of the reflections highlights four main themes centered around product adaptation, cultural and religious considerations, economic factors, and interactive learning experiences in global marketing. These themes emerge from the reflections of the students who

analyzed the global strategies of fast-food chains like KFC and McDonald's. Below are the key themes along with relevant excerpts to illustrate each:

3.1 Product Adaptation to Local Cultures and Preferences

Students consistently reflect on how fast-food chains adapt their menus to suit the cultural, religious, and local tastes of different markets. This adaptation is seen as a crucial strategy to attract local customers and meet their unique demands.

Each country has its own specially designed menu to attract customers based on their preferences, culture, and religion. (Fazira)

I better understand the concept of 'products adaptation' when I see KFC using local food to attract local buyers. (Amir)

By comparing KFC or McDonald's menus in other countries like Japan, we can learn how culture, local ingredients, and cooking styles influence the menus in different countries. (Azizu).

KFC might focus more on local spices and flavors, while McDonald's offers a wider variety with seasonal menus, not just local flavors. (Celine)

3.2 Cultural and Religious Sensitivity in Global Marketing

A significant theme is the respect for cultural and religious practices by fast-food brands in different countries. The students note how these companies modify their offerings to align with religious and cultural norms, ensuring their acceptance in diverse markets.

In India, the menu is based on chicken because the majority are Hindus and do not eat beef. This shows the company respects the culture and religion of the country. (Fazira)

McDonald's in India localized its products...to ensure that it incorporates the common local dishes. (Amir).

Through menu variations, we can appreciate how food can symbolize the culture of a nation. (Azizu)

3.3 Economic Factors and Pricing Strategies

Students reflect on how the prices of products are adjusted according to the purchasing power of local markets. The economic conditions of a country influence pricing, sales, and promotional strategies, which are essential for business success.

From a pricing perspective, we can learn about a country's economy by comparing prices from different countries and the average wage in those countries. (Adib)

I learned why it's important to set prices according to the purchasing power of the local community to ensure competitiveness with other products. (Amir)

3.4 Active and Interactive Learning Experience

A recurring theme is the effectiveness of experiential learning over theoretical study. Students find that comparing real-world examples of how fast-food chains operate across countries helps them grasp concepts better, stimulates creativity, and encourages critical thinking.

Students can think creatively about the marketing adaptation techniques of foreign companies in different countries using real-life situations. (Fazira)

If given a task, it would be more interesting because students can independently browse and compare different countries in terms of price, menu, and promotions. (Adib)

I think it's easier to understand when you have this experience yourself. It's different from just reading books or hearing others talk about it, compared to experiencing it practically. (Celine)

The reflections reveal that students gained a deeper understanding of how global brands tailor their products to local markets, emphasizing cultural respect, economic alignment, and the importance of interactive, hands-on learning. This analysis reflects a comprehensive approach to grasping global marketing strategies by engaging with real-world examples and fostering critical thinking and creativity.

4. DISCUSSION

The integration of live examples from brand websites demonstrates the importance of product adaptation in a way that theoretical models alone cannot. By seeing real-time adaptations and discussing them collaboratively, students can connect marketing theory with practice. The use of multimedia platforms and collaborative learning tools ensures that students remain engaged and apply what they learn to actual business scenarios. Collaborative platforms became very efficient and allow communication between high number of participants. University education involves many students, therefore, collaborative platforms proved to be very useful (Yasin & Abbas, 2021).

4.1 Product Adaptation to Local Cultures and Preferences

Product adaptation, as a core element of global marketing, requires an understanding of various cultural and regulatory environments (Levitt, 1983; Zou & Cavusgil, 2002). The imperatives of competition, always too harsh, the globalization of markets, the evolution of technologies and lifestyles, force companies to constantly adapt their strategies and products to the demands of ever more accelerated changes. Today, more and more managers realize that they can substantially improve their competitive strength by adopting aesthetics in the international conception of the enterprise (Gherasim & Gherasim, 2018). For instance, McDonald's entered the Chinese and Indian markets by catering to local preferences. During the Chinese New Year, McDonald's served Prosperity burgers in China and McSpicy chicken sandwiches in India (Kolhe, 2023).

4.2 Cultural and Religious Sensitivity in Global Marketing

Brands like McDonald's and KFC have achieved success in international markets by tailoring their product offerings to fit local preferences, religious practices, and dietary restrictions (Kolhe, 2023). Tailoring can also facilitate fast-food chains' ingress into new markets and distinguish them from rival entities (Sousa & da Silveira, 2019)

For example, In India, McDonald's is careful and ensures that it is sensitive to the religious understandings of the Indian people McDonald's in India localized its products to provide food that is nonstandard on its menu, such as lamb patties and Aloo Tikki Burger, which is a classic Indian vegetarian burger, to ensure that it incorporates the common local dishes. While KFC modifies its spice blends in various regions to suit local flavor preferences. McDonald's also provides vegetable pizza puffs that is unique to India and nowhere else in other parts of the world. Despite the importance of

these adaptations, traditional teaching methods in marketing courses often remain too theoretical and lack engagement with these real-world examples (Rajawat et al., 2020).

4.3 Economic Factors and Pricing Strategies

Economic factors, such as local purchasing power, inflation, and currency fluctuations, play a pivotal role in shaping the pricing strategies of multinational fast-food chains like McDonald's and KFC. These companies adjust their prices based on the economic realities of each market to remain competitive and profitable. As discussed by Alon et al., as reflected in research, comparing prices between countries allows companies to align their pricing with local economic conditions, ensuring competitiveness and profitability in diverse markets" (Alon et al., 2020

4.4 Active and Interactive Learning Experience

Theoretical Frameworks provided in textbooks cover aspects like standardization vs. adaptation (Alon et al., 2020) but they do not adequately equip students with hands-on exposure to how global marketing strategies are implemented in diverse markets. Research indicates that active learning methods, where students engage with real-world scenarios, foster better critical thinking and application of knowledge (Prince, 2004). Empirical studies showcased in the literature demonstrate that active learning improves academic achievement, conceptual understanding, critical thinking, motivation, and inclusiveness compared to traditional passive lecture formats. Substantial research shows active learning improves undergraduate students' learning outcomes, skills, and motivation compared to purely lecture-based courses (Dzaiy & Abdullah, 2024)

Furthermore, the use of digital tools like multimedia resources, websites, and collaborative platforms enhances student engagement and facilitates a more experiential learning process (Bonwell & Eison, 1991). The findings on this principle of student engagement can also be used to show that digital media can perpetuate unequal access to learning opportunities due to socio-economic differences (Zimba et al., 2021) Improved engagement and retention of learning experiences among students, high levels of interaction and teamwork for social development, the encouragement of constructive and learning experiences, and diversified exposure to practical knowledge to cope with real-world demands are the significant advantages for student learning in the virtual reality landscape (Asad et al., 2021).

Real-time interactive tools, such as visiting the websites of McDonald's and KFC in various countries, can bridge the gap between theory and practice. Undoubtedly, McDonald's has its own website in each of the nations where it operates. These official pages provide access to each country's unique menus, promotions, and advertising. Using these, students can quickly learn about the numerous ways the multinational firm localises its public image (DuBois, 2024). For instance, to prevent losses, companies in China need to adapt to local tastes and inclinations. Therefore, McDonald's implemented a policy to avoid using chicken breast flesh in favour of chicken thighs, which are preferred by Chinese consumers. McDonald's created a grilled chicken burger with curly fries to appeal to Chinese culture and tastes. This burger is popular around Chinese New Year. They used garlic sauce to gratify their consumers (Yue, 2023). By allowing students to explore these real-world adaptations, they gain a deeper understanding of international marketing strategies that go beyond the classroom theory.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the need for innovative teaching methods in international agricultural marketing is paramount to bridging the gap between theory and practice. Traditional teaching methods, relying on lectures and textbooks, fall short in engaging students with real-world scenarios, which are crucial for understanding product adaptation across diverse global markets. By incorporating active learning techniques, such as interactive digital tools and real-time case studies, students can develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, thus improving their grasp of international marketing strategies. The integration of multimedia and collaborative platforms not only enhances student engagement but also provides a more practical and holistic learning experience. These innovations will better prepare students for the dynamic and complex challenges they will encounter in the global marketplace.

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References

- Alon, I., Jaffe, E., Prange, C., & Vianelli, D. (2020). *Global marketing: strategy, practice, and cases*. Routledge.
- Asad, M.M., Naz, A., Churi, P., & Tahanzadeh, M.M. (2021). Virtual reality as pedagogical tool to enhance experiential learning: a systematic literature review. *Education Research International*, 2021(1), 7061623.
- Casado-Aranda, L.A., Sánchez-Fernández, J., Montoro-Ríos, F. J., & Horcajadas, M. I. A. (2021). Evaluation of the work-integrated learning methodology: Teaching marketing through practitioner experience in the classroom. *Mathematics*, 9(17), 2164.
- DuBois, T. D. (2024). Fast Food for Thought: Finding Global History in a Beijing McDonald's. *World History Connected*, 21(1).
- Dzaiy, A. H. S., & Abdullah, S. A. (2024). The use of active learning strategies to foster effective teaching in higher education institutions. *Zanco Journal of Human Sciences*, 28(4), 328-351.
- Gherasim, A., & Gherasim, D. (2018). Cultural Environment in International Marketing. *Economy Transdisciplinarity Cognition*, 21(1).
- Gilmore, A., McAuley, A., Miles, M. P., & Pattinson, H. (2020). Four questions of entrepreneurial marketing education: Perspectives of university educators. *Journal of Business Research*, 113, 189-197. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.12.016>
- Greenberg, B. (2021). Teaching Critically: Utilizing History To Explore And Examine How Diversity Impacts Marketing. *Diversity for a New Decade*, 32.
- Harding, L. M., & Alexander, J. F. (2019). Teaching Innovations That Work The (Marketing) Plan, (29), 105-106
- Kolhe, A. (2023). Exploring the Factors Constraining the Adoption of Multi-domestic Strategy Among the Fast-Food Chains: A Case Study of Fast-Food Chains in Europe Dublin, National College of Ireland.
- Molin, S., & Sjöberg, A. (2017). Addressing the Gap between Theory and Practice-A Marketing-as-Practice Approach.
- Rajawat, A., Kee, D., Malik, M., Qayumm, M., Shaffie, M., Fuaat, M., AlDosari, N., & Santoso, M. (2020). Factors: Responsible for McDonald's Performance. *Journal of The Community Development in Asia*, 3, 11-17. <https://doi.org/10.32535/jcda.v3i2.806>

- Sousa, R., & da Silveira, G. J. C. (2019). The relationship between servitization and product customization strategies. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 39(3), 454-474. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-03-2018-0177>
- Thanasi-Boçe, M. (2020). Enhancing students' entrepreneurial capacity through marketing simulation games. *Education+ Training*, 62(9), 999-1013.
- Yasin, A. A., & Abbas, A. (2021, 21-23 April 2021). Role of gamification in Engineering Education: A systematic literature review. 2021 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON).
- Yue, D. (2023). Analysis on McDonald's Localization Strategy. *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences*, 10, 46-50. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/10/20230426>
- Zimba, Z. F., Khosa, P., & Pillay, R. (2021). Using blended learning in South African social work education to facilitate student engagement. *Social Work Education*, 40(2), 263-278. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2020.1746261>